

LIFE-STYLE MARKETING: AN ALTERNATIVE THEORETICAL MODEL OF SERVICE MARKETING DIMENSION (AN EMPIRICAL STUDY ON BEAUTY SALON CUSTOMERS IN JAKARTA)

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Abstract: *Beauty salon business is fast growing in line with the economic growth and changes in modern life-style. In such a situation, whereby market potential also rapidly advances, low life-time sustainability of beauty salon industry prevails. Indicated by the shifting in customer requirements, beauty salon services orientation should adapt to the changes in the customer requirements in order to survive.*

This research was conducted to identify beauty salon customer requirements nowadays. A new requirement was identified, i.e. life-style–besides the already existing marketing mix requirements. The expected final objective of this research is to define life-time sustainability using correct marketing mix.

Keywords: *service marketing, service marketing mix, life-style marketing, customer behavior, customer requirement.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Market potential that develops along with the growth in the number and income of the population is not always advantageous for beauty salon business. The first-mover advantage is not always right for the present condition, in the sense that first-companies will always win the competition [Liebowitz, 2003]. This fact is also true in the beauty industry such as beauty salon that does not always constitute a venture pioneered in an emerging market that later grows into a market leader. Despite the continuing growth of beauty salon market potential in Jakarta, it does not guarantee the growth rate in the revenue, number of clients, and average spending per client. The end of a beauty salon business is a result of business setback and insufficient profit making. Strongly suspected factor in this case is the inability of a salon in fulfilling the need of customer requirements in terms of the

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demand of time. One of the indications of the change in the orientation of beauty salon consumers' need based on the findings of previous studies is the need for modern life-style. This situation is a result of the insufficient capability of the beauty salon marketing management in addressing the requirements of the customers that leads to the customer value gap.

Based on the analysis of the above issues, failure in overcoming such conditions will result in the inability of beauty salons in retaining their customers' loyalty, and the difficulty in building a profitable business which will ultimately results in the loss suffered by the salons and ultimately the loss of their business.

The research is focused on the requirements of salon customers in Jakarta that are used as a benchmark for the Indonesian life-style to analyze beauty salon service customers by including the indication of the need for life-style. This study confirms the theory of service marketing dimension, namely service marketing mix using attributes that are significant and suitable with the specific characteristics of beauty salons. Furthermore, this study also explores a new dimension of life-style characteristics as a new need of beauty salon customers.

This study is expected to provide an alternative for the development of specific theories in beauty salon service marketing that can be concretely applied to suit the specific characteristics of the industry and the recent condition of customer requirements.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Service Marketing in Beauty Salon Service

According to Rust *et. al.* [1996], due to the intangible nature of the service, attempts to meet the need of customers and to provide customer satisfaction, service comprises four principle components, namely: service delivery, service product, service environment, and physical product. The typical nature of service business requires specific marketing that relies on taste and the quality of the service which depends on the service provider [Alma, 2013]. Service also constitutes a business system [Kotler, 2000]. Furthermore, in terms of service delivery system, it responds to the questions of 'how', 'where', and 'when' the service product is delivered to consumers [Lovelock, 1991]. Service often includes important tangible components as well as expert personnel that constitute dominant combination in the series of value creation for service performance [Lovelock and Wirtz, 2004]. With service, the contact made by such personnel with customers constitutes the moment of truth that leads to the delivery process that involves consumers in the provision of their expectation [Lovelock and Wirtz, 2004]. There are 3 dimensions of relationship in this case, namely:

1. reach, which is the dimension of obtaining an access and connection with consumers,
2. richness, which is the dimension for finding the reciprocity flow, and
3. affiliation, which is the dimension for the determination of facilities used for in the interaction with consumers [Hitt *et. al.*, 2005].

These levels of relationship play highly important role in beauty salons, in line with the service delivery system model, namely high contact service as proposed by Lovelock and Wirtz [2004] whereby the point of agreement between consumers and salon service providers in the service delivery occurs in tangible factors constituting interior and exterior facilities, equipment and service people as a visible process that can be observed by consumers (front stage).

The success of a beauty salon in selling the concept of well-being, beauty and fashion as well as the fulfillment of life-style need makes the perception factor highly critical in measuring the level of consumer satisfaction. Consumers decide their need and emphasize on emotional and experience factors. As such, the management of a salon specifically constitutes a combination of art, science, management, intuition, life-cycle and experience. Customer relationship is built initially through first-impression [Evans *et. al.*, 2000]. Customer relationship is also considered imperative in improving service loyalty [Bove and Johnson, 2006].

In beauty salon industry, the operation also constitutes a critical element in supporting the salon to render superior services. Several requirements that have to be met in beauty salon operation comprise safety and hygiene that directly and indirectly constitute part of the salon's total service [Hatton, 1996], including the safety and health of the salon customers [Cressy, 2003].

2.2 Customer Behavior

Customer behavior is driven by the factor of the unfulfilment of an individual's needs, wants, and desire that leads to a tension. This tension triggers an individual to behave as such to achieve the desired goals [Schiffman and Kanuk, 2000]. Based on the theory of motivation, it can be linked with and explained by Maslow Hierarchy theory of need. Compared with highly individualistic Western society, Asian people have distinctive characteristics [Schutte, 1998].

Human beings are affected by psychological factors that are attached to every individual, such as motivation, perception, learning, personality, and attitude, that will react to external inputs and will affect the recognition of need, and search for information prior to purchase making and the evaluation of various alternatives [Schiffman and Kanuk, 2000].

Figure 2.1: Comparison of the Theory of Motivation and the Western and Asian Maslow Need

Source: The Adaptation of Maslow's Model [Sheldrake, 1996] and Schutte [1998]

As stated by Hawkins *et. al.* [2007], consumer decision process starts from the interaction between external and internal factors that affects individual's self-concept and life-style that drive the needs and desires for decision making process. The feed-back of post-purchase will act as an input that constitutes the exploration of the suitability with the external and internal influences (experiences and acquisitions).

The above view is in line with that of Kurtz and Clow [1998] on the purchase decision made by consumers (pre-purchase phase) being affected by internal factors, external factors, firm-produced factors, and risks. Internal factors consist of the individual needs and wants of consumers, past experiences, expectations, and the level of involvement. Mulyadi [2005] defines consumer's internal factors as: motivation, perception, learning, personality, and attitude. As confirmed also by Kotler [2003], psychological factors come from inside an individual and consist of motivation, perception learning, personality, memory, emotion, belief, and attitude. Psychological factors as proposed by Peter and Olson [2005] are categorized in two groups, namely: affective and cognitive elements. Affective refers to emotional responses (emotions, feelings, or moods), and cognition refers to mental (thinking) responses (knowledge, meanings, and beliefs). Affective and cognitive elements constitute two inter-related systems.

Figure 2.2: Consumer's Decision Making Process

Source: Hawkins et. al. [2007]

2.3 Life-style

Life-style can be used as one of the ways for segmentation, and segmentation based on life-style can be categorized based on the manners of time spending for activity, trust, and socioeconomic characteristics, such as income and education [Lamb et. al., 2002].

Life-style as part of customer behavior is defined as follows:

Table 2.1
Definition of Life-style

Definition	Source
Materialization of the activities, interests, and opinions in the life of a social grup that interacts with its environment.	Walker et. al. [1999]
Life-style reflects human activities in the use of time, the interest in matters that are considered important, and the opinions about oneself or others, and reflects the basic character experienced in life.	John Plummer in Engel et. al. [2001]
Indicates one's behavioral life pattern in spending and allocating time	Mowen [2001]

Cont. table 2.1

Definition	Source
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. This is the manner in which the individual copes and deals with his/her psychological and physical environment on a day-to-day basis. More specifically, it is used by some theorists as a phrase describing the values, attitudes, opinions, and behavior patterns of the consumer. 2. The manner in which people conduct their lives, including their activities, interests, and opinions 	American Marketing Association
Individual's behavior is manifested in the form of one's activities, interest, and view to actualize one's personality due to the influence of the interaction with one's environment.	This research adopts the view of John Plummer in Engel <i>et. al.</i> [2001]

The study on life-style that focuses on the dimension of life-style and the relation with social class, was conducted by Smith and Lutz [1996], that generated three dimensions, namely centrality (experiences central to one's life), happiness (experiences essential to happiness) and success (experiences reflecting success).

Figure 2.3: Discretionary Product Matrix

Source: Danziger [2004]

Discretionary purchase is divided into four categories that can be represented by two vertical and horizontal lines to describe discretionary spending [Danziger, 2004]. The approach of this life-style category is more of individual characteristics rather than life-style categorizing based on people's life routine. As such, it would be more appropriate to use in studies on spending motivation and requirements in beauty salon service. Spending motivation and pattern is related to the personality element in consumer behaviour and is viewed as consistent response to the stimulus from the environment.

Studies on this personality element are divided in three groups, namely: psychoanalysis, socio-psychology, and trait factor [Engel, 2001]. An example of behaviour described by the above theories is Hedonic. Principally humans are motivated to lead and enjoy a good life. This nature is another form of behaviour of a group in the society that can be profitably made use of in creating demand. The hedonic group of consumers tend to spend their money. They tend to be consumptive unlike the utilitarian group who spend their money in accordance with the use or purpose [Okada, 2005]. Hedonic also constitutes a lifestyle that prioritizes indulgence and extravagance [Holt, 1997]. It refers to the need of consumers for using products or services in creating phantasy and sensation, and to obtain emotional drive [Mowen and Minor, 2001].

2.4 Marketing Mix-services

The description of competencies in service marketing management is related to the policy of marketing mix-services. Marketing-mix service constitutes 4 Ps marketing-mix that is completed with 3 Ps that are typically applicable to services, namely: people, process, and physical-evidence. [Tjiptono and Chandra, 2011] add psychological factor to those, which plays a specifically important role in services since it has strong influence on the emotional factor, particularly on beauty salon industry services [Widjaja, 2010].

As a note to the above model, the importance of people knowledge is supported by the opinion of Gouthier and Schmid [2003] that include consumer knowledge element as part of service process by the consumers in the form of consumer participation in service acceptance process. As such, the 4 Ps marketing mix comprises people, process, physical-evidence, and participating customer [Stauss, 2005].

Based on the above theoretical description, of varied views on marketing mix components, those that can be related to beauty salon services are as follows:

Table 2.2
Beauty Salon Service Marketing Mix

<i>Marketing Mix Components</i>	<i>Source</i>
Product (service)	Zeithaml and Bitner [1996], Glyn and Barnes [1996], Rust <i>et. al.</i> [1996], Kotler [2000], Hadisuwarno <i>et. al.</i> [2004], Tjiptono [2011],
Price	Tjiptono and Chandra [2011], Hurriyati [2005], Zeithaml <i>et. al.</i> [2006].
Place	
Promotion	
People	
Process	
Physical Evidence	
Public Relation	Hadisuwarno <i>et. al.</i> [2004]
Productivity and Quality	Lovelock and Wright [2005]
Participating Customer	Gouthier and Schmid [2003], Stauss [2005]
Personnel Loyalty	Bove and Johnson, [2006]
Psychographics	Widjaja [2010]
People Knowledge	

2.5 Customer Loyalty

In post-purchase phase customers evaluate the quality of the whole services received, whether satisfaction or dissatisfaction. Satisfied customers will take post-purchase actions, including repeat purchase, customer loyalty, and positive word of mouth, whereas dissatisfied customer would perform vendor switching dan make negative word of mouth communications. Satisfaction on long term base creates customer loyalty that is gradually formed by cognitive, affective, conative, and action types of loyalty [Oliver, 1997].

Satisfaction value may create loyalty in long term, if the creation value is on the acceptable level and is in accordance with the condition of the customers. Customers stop returning or make less spending due to the decrease in the product or service value as a result of higher value provided by competitors in consumers' perception or may also be caused by boring experience [Arussy, 2006]. The importance of customer loyalty compared to customer satisfaction was supported by the findings of studies conducted in the US indicating that satisfaction did not have any reliable relation to the increase in sales and profit. When customer satisfaction is no longer reliable, the appropriate measure for repeat purchase should be referred to as customer loyalty [Griffin, 2002].

The process of beauty salon consumers' spending is often led by the customers' satisfaction and affection for their regular salons. Satisfied customers often promote salons by word of mouth and indirectly act as the salons' partners and ambassadors without any compensation. Similar case occurs with the consumer pattern in Europe. In this case, previous experience is mostly critical in establishing opinions

that occurs in the word of mouth promotion [Nielsen, 2006]. Maintaining customer loyalty is the most critical factor in improving the profit performance of a company [Walker *et. al.*, 2013]. Loyal consumers are willing to pay more than the normal rate and often willingly perform word of mouth marketing, although based on the research conducted by Reinartz and Kumar [2002], no solid correlation was found between loyalty and profitability.

Based on the above dialectic discussion, the current development indicates marketing orientation that does not only rely on customer satisfaction [Schneider and Bowen, 1999] to generate customer loyalty, and that only delighted customers will be loyal ones [Verma, 2003].

2.6 Conceptual Framework

Customer satisfaction is the foundation of the efforts to maintain competitive position although it does not always guarantee sufficient customer value to ensure customer loyalty. Customer behaviour starts from the drive resulting from one's unsatisfied needs, wants, and desires that lead to a tension that will be an important factor in influencing subsequent behaviours [Schiffman and Kanuk, 2000]. When this happens, the level of customer loyalty will be affected and will ultimately lead to customer churn. Therefore, being a market leader or pioneer does not secure customer satisfaction and the creation of customer loyalty [Liebowitz, 2003].

The model for this study was emphasized on the increase in the effectiveness of service marketing that suits beauty salon services. Using the support of seven Ps mix theory, namely: product, price, place, promotion, people, process, and physical evidence [Zeithaml *et. al.*, 2006], a review had to be made to find the most appropriate combination for beauty salon services. The use of 7 Ps marketing-mix service approach was not sufficient and had to be linked with the marketing mix paradigm, namely psychographic to explain the life-style factor [Widjaja, 2010].

The life-style phenomenon becomes a paradigm in beauty salon service marketing. On the other hand, individuals also have their own personal motivations that affect their behaviours in line with Maslow hierarchical theory [Schutte, 1998] and trait factor [Engel, 2001]. In the exploratory preliminary research, it was indicated that in addition to the need for beauty salon service that is fulfilled by service mix, there was a strong indication of the need element that related to life-style. This indication was seen in the attachment (Focus Group Discussion findings). Indicators suspected as life-style components were grouped as temporary presumptions of life-style dimensions, namely: luxury, indulgence Danziger [2004], self-concept [Hawkins *et. al.*, 2007] and admired Schutte [1998]. Life style dimension built with indicator elements that were indicated in the exploratory research,

Figure 2.4: Research Conceptual Framework

despite the exploration conducted during the research was not as solid as that of service combination model. An attribute was indicated as being included despite having not openly and explicitly expressed by beauty salon consumers in the exploratory research.

Marketing effort performance also directly affects customer loyalty. The model for the research on the relation of marketing effort performance and service performance that was formulated as the level of customer satisfaction was proposed by Wong and Sohal [2003], while that of the relation of marketing effort performance and customer loyalty was composed by Olsen and Johnson [2003]. Based on these ideas, the model for this research was built using the model of the relation of service performance and life-style as a construct that affects customer loyalty as specified below.

The frame of mind of this research was prepared using process delivery approach. As beauty salons and the customers conduct are in an interaction process of providing and receiving services, the interaction becomes a critical moment of

Figure 4.1: Scree Plot Result of the Analysis Factor of 73 Beauty Salon Service Attributes
Source: Research Findings, n = 400.

truth, and the service provider has to maximize the interaction to fulfil the need and desire of the customers in accordance with the dimensional priority of the service and the life-style.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

The research was conducted by way of a survey on 400 high-class (A) and middle-class (B) salon customers in Jakarta as respondents. The preliminary stage that constituted an explorative study was meant to determine the specific attributes/factors for the service mix dimension and to examine the phenomenon of any indication of life-style mix. This explorative study was performed using focus group discussions (FGD) technique and in-depth interviews. Based on the screening and general categorizing as a result of the FGD, variables were found that comprised respondents' opinion of the salon regarding the expected service need as well as the behaviour of the salon's respondents. To confirm the 7 P service mix, confirmatory factorial analysis was used, while explorational factorial analysis was used to formulate the need for life-style.

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the attributes selected during the FGD to reflect the need of salon consumers, a KMO test was performed on all the selected attributes and Bartlett's Test was performed of the data of 400 respondents based on the result of a survey. The research findings generated MSA and Bartlett test sparsity of 0.676 and indicated significant confidence level of 0.01. The MSA test on the data using

73 attributes generated a satisfactory result that could be used in the process to reflect the need for beauty salon service. In the result of further test using the following scree plot Figure, the 73 attributes were grouped into 11 or 12 factors. The grouping of 11 factors provided an explanation of 68.25% need for beauty salon service, while the use of 12 factors provided an explanation of the need of customers totaling at 70.09%.

Based on the selected attributes, the basic approach of the theories of product, price, place, promotion, people, process and physical evidence were used for the grouping of service mix (SERV). The grouping was performed with KMO (MSA) testing using the scores as included in Table 4.1 indicating that the attributes used were quite appropriate and applicable, while Barlett's test of sphericity was 0.000 (significant), indicating that the attributes used in the grouping as a whole correlated significantly and properly explained the measured factors. Based on the anti-image correlation test, all the grouped attributes had more than 0.5 score indicating that each attribute had sufficiently strong inter-correlation of the factor forming attributes. The result of the component matrix also indicated that each attribute had a score of more than 0.5.

Table 4.1
Beauty Salon Service Mix

<i>Factor</i>	<i>KMO (MSA) Test</i>
Product	.844
Price	.694
Place	.555
Promotion	.565
People	.849
Process	.764

Source: Research Findings, $n = 400$.

On the basis of the above seven factors, the service mix (SERV) of beauty salon service as a result of the attribute improvement are as follows:

<i>Product (Service)</i>	<i>People</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Beautifying • Skin whitening • Making figure look appealing • Rejuvenating • Skin clarifying • Skin tightening • Making hair manageable • Hair softening • Making hair look brilliant • Using high-quality products • Using domestic products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Friendly • Patient • Skillful • Pleasant treatment • Not overly talkative • Staff focused at work • Remember people's taste • Familiar stylists

Cont. figure 4.2

<i>Price</i>	<i>Process</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discount • Price matches quality • Price matches budget 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sparse visitors • No wait-up time • Comfortable • Hotel-like service
<i>Place</i>	<i>Physical Evidence</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic location • Located near housing area • Located in commercial area 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Well shaded parking • Fresh bouquet aroma • Comfortable seats • Music suitable to taste • TV channels suitable to taste • Clean • Tranquil
<i>Promotion</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frequently advertised and well- known • Visible signage • Attractive promotion 	

Figure 4.2: Beauty Salon Service Mix (SERV)

Furthermore, in building this model, in addition to SERV, life-style model was also built with elements comprising attributes as indicated in exploratory studies, although the result of the exploratory study was not as solid as that of the model service mix (SERV). There were attributes being included although they were not explicitly expressed by salon consumers in the exploratory study. The life style model defines that life-style suspected of being highly important customer requirement is divided into motivations. The measuring of life-style was conducted by indirect parameter through the underlying motivation of consumer life-style behaviour.

In the LIST component determination, decision was made of the attributes that were not included in the SERV group. Attributes that were used at this stage were the results of anti-image correlation selection with a score of more than 0.5. Based on these results, the selected attributes were stated as appropriate for further test, namely to determine the number of factors that were suitable and could sufficiently reflect the LIST measure. The scree plot test result is depicted as follows:

The result in the above Figure reflects that there were four factors formed, and those factors were seen as representing and explaining a LIST of 74.5%. On the basis of this analysis, the formed factors were grouped and each group of factors was tested. The groups based on the characteristics were referred to as: luxury, indulgence, self-concept, and admired. The result of KMO (MSA) test is depicted in Table 4.2, and the attributes used were considered sufficiently satisfactory and

Figure 4.3: Scree Plot Result of Beauty Salon Service Life-style Analysis Factor

Source: Research Findings, $n = 400$.

applicable, indicating that the attributes used in this grouping in overall correlated significantly and appropriately explained the measured factors.

Table 4.2
Beauty Salon Service Lifestyle Mix

Factor	KMO (MSA) Test
Luxury	.692
Indulgence	.725
Self-concept	.732
Admired	.510

Source: Research Findings, $n = 400$.

Based on the anti-image correlation test, all grouped attributes had more than 0.5 score which indicated that each attribute had sufficiently strong correlation of the factor forming attributes. The result of the component matrix also indicated that each attribute had a score of more than 0.5.

The result of the above research provides an information of the attributes that are considered important by customers in beauty salon service provision that form life-style related dimensions. Attributes that are highly specific are generalized into broader and more general characters based on the theories of basic motivation, customer behavior and life-style behavior. On the other hand, attributes that are overly general are enhanced to be more specific in explaining about life-style. The life-style mix as well as the specific attributes for beauty salon services are as follows:

<i>Luxury</i>	<i>Self-concept</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Giving an impression of luxury • Using prestigious brands • Rendering royal quality services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved self-image • Reflecting self-performance • Giving different look • Supporting one's profession
<i>Indulgence</i>	<i>Admired</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refreshing place • Good use of spare time • Providing pleasure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Admired by other people • Becoming a center of attention • Becoming a fashion setter

Figure 4.4: Life-Style Mix (LIST) in Beauty Salon Service

The result of the above factorial analysis confirms that life-style factor model in beauty salon service is important and cannot be ignored. Life-style components that support the research model are built based on the theories of motivation, customer behavior, and life-style behavior, such as literature review, that particularly comprise the following opinions:

Engel *et. al.* [2001]; Wells, quoted by Engel *et. al.* [2001]; Cathelat [1994]; Rokeach, in Cathelat [1994: 93]; Max Weber and Karl Marx, quoted by Engel *et. al.* [2001]; Yankelovich in Cathelat [1994]; Bearden and Etzel, quoted by Engel *et. al.* [2001]; Maslow, quoted by Sheldrake [1996]; Kurtz and Clow [1998]; Walker [2013]; Kotler [1999]; Lamb *et. al.* [2002]; Kotler, [2003]; Cressy [2003]; Tjiptono [2011]; Hitt *et. al.* [2005] and Hawkins *et. al.* [2007].

The findings of this study generate a model that consists of eleven variables that form a construct service mix (SERV) and life-style mix (LIST). SERV comprises seven dimensions with 38 attributes, namely: product (11 attributes), price (3 attributes), place (2 attributes), promotion (3 attributes), people (8 attributes), process (4 attributes), and physical evidence (7 attributes). LIST consists of four dimensions with 13 attributes, namely: luxury (3 attributes), indulgence (3 attributes), self-concept (4 attributes), and admired (3 attributes). SERV confirms the existing service marketing theories. However, the specification of the attributes are particular to beauty salon service industry, and LIST is composed of the results of the exploratory study in this research. Based on the result of the analysis, the model used for this study that reflects the above life-style has luxury, indulgence, self-concept and admired dimensions that are abbreviated to LISA.

5. CONCLUSION

Beauty salon service includes characteristic attributes that specifically suit the need of beauty salon service customers. Attention to attributes that play important roles on the salon customers can fulfil the customer requirements to enable beauty salons

to provide optimal customer value. By paying attention to the particularity of attributes that are important for generating optimal customer value, the performance of salon services will render optimal functional benefit through the service marketing mix dimension, namely product, price, place, promotion, people, process, and physical evidence. On the other hand, beauty salon service has a dimension of providing customer value in the form of emotional benefits comprising: luxury, indulgence, self-concept, and admired (LISA) elements that constitute crucial dimensions that deserve serious attention.

This research is a preliminary study of the application of life-style in beauty industry service that requires intensification for the development of further service marketing theory that on a broader scale can be applicable in other life-style related industries.

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